

Building World Class Indian Cities By Strengthening Municipal Finance

Manjeet Kumar¹ & Alpa Singh²

1. JRF Political Science, CCS University, Meerut, UP Email: manjeet.kumar3426@gmail.com
2. HOD, Political Science, MMH College, CCS University, Meerut, UP, India

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Abstract

Modern cities have to buckle up to respond to increasing urbanization demands. Here municipal finance becomes the connecting link in strengthening overall quality of urban life. The proposed study will research to augment the municipal finance of Indian cities and strengthen it further, thus strengthening the quality of overall city administration.

Key words: Municipal Finance, Indian Cities.

Introduction

Cities symbolize the pinnacle of material achievement of human civilization as reflected in towering skyscrapers, fast multimodal transport amenities at the doorstep.

Census 2011 of India had pointed towards growing urban population trends which though standing at 22% during that time, is expected to grow further exponentially in future. Thus, 74th Amendment Act 1992 was path breaking in the sense of strengthening city governance by establishing the third tier of participative democracy.

However the creaky overstrained urban infrastructure as reflected in polluted air inviting “gas chamber” remarks from noted environmentalists, unhygienic slums, crowded transport, recent urban floods point towards the serious shortcomings in municipal administration. As noted Indian philosopher Kautilya had noted “Dharmasya moolam Artha, Artha moolam Rajyam”, Finance is a critical aspect of administration. Municipal sources of finance consist of taxes, grants and transfer from state and central governments. Still Indian municipal cities generate mere Four Percentage of GDP from own revenues.

What Is A World Class City:

Though there can be no “one-size-fit-all” template, still the concern for qualitative ease of living remains the cherished goal of any city administration. Thus, some attributes which can be termed global cutting across borders are— well functioning infrastructure in the form of whether public transport or amenities like water supply, housing etc.

Added to these, the egalitarian inclusiveness as highlighted under Sustainable Development Goals, is a must. Take for example Tokyo planning for safer movement of visually challenged citizens. Hence comes the need of an institutional structure governing cities which has to be truly participative to be termed global. Not to restrict the definition to mere materialistic attributes, a world class city must be modelled on the concept of circular economy to be sustainable. The mantras of reduce, reuse and recycle takes care of present and future generations. In the twenty-first century, technology has been the enabler of heralding a truly World class city. Hence use of artificial intelligence, big data, drones etc

enhance level of governance bringing city in tune with global standards-efficient and sustainable.

City Governance in India

Indian urban governance can trace its roots as far back as Indus valley civilization well planned drainage system. Later even during Mauryan or Cholas rule, one can find evidence of well administered Nagars. Modern urban administration came into being with Madras taking the lead, strengthened further by then colonial Viceroy Lord Ripon Resolution. Post independence Seventy-Fourth Amendment Act 1992 gave constitutional recognition to city administration. AMRUT and JNNURM schemes brought about facelift for Indian cities. State Finance Commissions have augmented the capabilities of city administration. Muni bonds success point towards the gaining credibility city governance has garnered pointing towards the critical role "Finance" is playing towards heralding birth of world class cities.

Dimensions of Municipal Finance

Indian cities have been constitutionally provided with own sources of revenue like property tax apart from the gap filling role played by State Finance Commission. At the same time grants and aids provided by respective State Government and scheme specific funds devolution by Central Government further bolster the financial coffers of urban local bodies in the country. However, Indian cities revenue contribute a paltry 0.75% towards the national Gross Domestic Product as compared to more than 6% in global counterparts.

Suggestions to Strengthen Municipal Finance

- Ensuring regular disbursement of funds mandated for urban local bodies by state governments.
- Strengthening capacity of urban local bodies to generate own source of revenue.
- Strengthening State Finance Commission where Central Finance Commission should play a more pro active handholding role.
- Exploring new avenues of finance for example Municipal Bonds with State Government and Central Government facilitating the same.
- Global Best practices can be incorporated by fine tuning them within Indian context. C40 can serve as a handy Forum here.
- Out of the box ideas like Transferrable Development Rights or Betterment Levy must be institutionalized.
- A fixed percentage of direct or indirect tax from a well functioning urban local body can be granted so as to incentivise better performance by other urban local bodies .
- Additionally ensuring Fiscal Responsibility of urban local bodies via fully functional accrual accounting and transparency disclosure must be Ensured.

Conclusion :-

As urbanization is on the rise, it is high time to strengthen municipal governance for sustainable economic growth. It is in this context financial strengthening of urban local bodies can be a game changer. More finance would ensure proper dovetailing of resources towards priority areas creating multiplier effect for the economy which in turn would generate more revenues and prosperity.

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